

Knockdown times in a simple assay determination of insecticide resistance in malaria vectors.

Jacques D. Charlwood ^{a,1,*} and Ayubo Kampango ^{a,2,3}.

a MOZDAN, P.O. Box 8, Morrumbene, Inhambane Province, Mozambique

*Corresponding author: Tel: +351 932340993, E-mail: jdcharlwood@gmail.com

1 Present address: Global Health and Tropical Medicine, Instituto de Higiene e Medicina Tropical, Lisbon, Portugal

2 Instituto Nacional de Saúde, Maputo, Mozambique

3 Department of Zoology and Entomology, University of Pretoria, Pretoria, South Africa

Abstract

Background

Determining the insecticide resistance status of malaria vectors, particularly to insecticides used on mosquito nets, is important but is limited to a relatively small number of locations. We describe a simple assay that enables this information to be obtained over a much wider range.

Methods

Time to knockdown of mosquitoes in an insecticide-treated netting-covered metal frame cage are recorded. The shape of the curve of proportion knocked down provides information on resistance status.

Results

Resistant *Anopheles funestus* took significantly longer for knockdown than did a susceptible *An. arabiensis*.

Conclusions

This simple technique would enable a wide range of locations to be sampled enhancing our understanding of the spread of resistance to pyrethroids.

Key words

Insecticide resistance, Insecticide-treated bednets, Malaria, Mosquito vectors,

Background

Mosquito nets treated with insecticide remain the main means of malaria control worldwide. Resistance to the insecticides used on the nets is, however, an increasing problem¹. Presently the standard tests to determine resistance status in the vectors require a laboratory and a reasonable degree of training in the person doing the testing². This limits the number of locations from which data is available and makes decision making harder. New, and simpler tests, which may help in indicating the development of resistance and that can be widely used are needed³. Here we describe a simple assay that can be performed without the need of a laboratory or sophisticated equipment and which may provide information on the development of resistance in the mosquitoes.

Methods

An unused insecticide treated net is wrapped around a wire frame cage (15cms on a side) and field collected mosquitoes are introduced. The time to knockdown is recorded. A similar cage covered with an untreated net is the control. If necessary, insects can be removed when they fall and can be stored individually by time of knockdown. Thus, supposing there was a mixture of two species in the collection (e.g. *Anopheles gambiae* and *An. coluzzii*) with a different resistance status they could be identified post-test (and individual curves developed as a result). The cumulative total number of mosquitoes knocked down is plotted over time and the resulting curve compared to a set of (yet to be developed) standard curves.

Results and Discussion

In the tests described, as an example of the possible range of outcomes, mosquitoes were collected, in the field, using Furvela tent-traps⁴. The tests were carried out with the nets that we had available. After removal from the trap mosquitoes were held for an hour before being assigned to either control or treatment cages. We did not have access to an untreated Olyset net for that particular control and so used a standard polyester net for this. Numbers knocked down per minute were recorded and plotted as a percentage of the total knocked down (Fig 1). In the case of resistant insects, the tests were stopped after one hour. In the present experiments none of the insects in the control cages were knocked down.

The average exposure time required to knockdown 50% ($KDT_{50} \pm 95\% \text{ CI}$) and 95% ($KDT_{95} \pm 95\% \text{ CI}$) of a resistant population of *An. funestus* from Mozambique when exposed to the Interceptor net was 55.4 (53.2 - 57.6) and 341.3 (296.1 - 386.5) minutes, respectively. The estimated KDT_{50} and KDT_{95} on exposure to a new, unused, Permanet were 42.4 (40.4 - 44.3) and 86.3 (74.9 - 97.7) minutes but the KDT_{50} and KDT_{95} for a susceptible population of *An. arabiensis* from Muleba, Tanzania, exposed to a new, unused, Olyset net was only 6.64 (6.15 - 7.14) and 13.40 (11.51 - 15.29) minutes. These are the kind of difference that might be seen between resistant and susceptible populations elsewhere. Should resistance begin to develop in a population then the curve will tend towards the right.

Given that LLINs remain the most widely used method of vector control, testing insecticides used for Indoor Residual Spraying (IRS) in this way is less important. The provision of pre-treated netting with the insecticides used for IRS, could also be produced for this purpose if required.

Conclusions

This simple test requires very little equipment, and does not require a laboratory. This would enable a wide geographical spread of tests to be undertaken. It could easily be added to other tests to obtain greater insight into the spread and development of resistance to insecticides by vectors. The development of standard curves would allow comparison with presently used techniques (such as the WHO or CDC tests). If necessary, this test can then be followed up using conventional techniques. Widespread use would allow decision makers to more easily determine the spread and intensity of resistance and so should inform future policy.

Declarations

Authors contributions: JDC conceived the study; JDC and AK designed the study protocol; AK and JDC carried out the assays; AK carried out the analysis of the data. JDC and AK drafted the manuscript; JDC and AK critically revised the manuscript for intellectual content. Both authors read and approved the final manuscript. JDC and AK are guarantors of the paper.

Funding: The work in Tanzania was funded by the Joint Global Health Trials Scheme of the UK Department for International Development, Medical Research Council, and Wellcome Trust (MR/L004437/) whilst a Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation Grand Challenge Project ('Turning houses into traps for mosquitoes') financed the study in Mozambique.

Conflict of interest: The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest

Ethics: The collections conducted in Tanzania were done as a component of the Pan African Malaria Vector Research Consortium project 'Evaluation of a novel long lasting insecticidal net and indoor residual spray product, separately and together, against malaria transmitted by pyrethroid resistant mosquitoes' which received ethical clearance from the ethics review committees of the Kilimanjaro Christian Medical College (certificate number 781 on the 16 September 2014), the Tanzanian National Institute for Medical Research (20 August 2014), and the London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine (reference 6551 on 24 July 2014). The collections in Mozambique took place under the aegis of the joint INS- DBL project 'Turning houses into traps for mosquitoes' which obtained ethical clearance from the National Bioethics Committee of Mozambique on the 2nd April 2001 (Ref: 056/CNBS/01).

Acknowledgements

We thank Erzelia V. E. Tómas for help in collecting the mosquitoes and conducting the assays. We also thank the reviewers for their constructive criticism of an earlier draft of the paper.

References

¹ Ndiath MO. Insecticides and Insecticide Resistance. *Methods Mol Biol* 2019; **2013**:287-304.

² WHO. Test procedures for insecticide resistance monitoring in malaria vector mosquitoes. World Health Organization. Geneva, 2013. ISBN 978 92 4 150515 4

³ Boyer S, Pothin E, Randriamaherijaona S, et al. Testing bio-efficacy of insecticide-treated nets with fewer mosquitoes for enhanced malaria control. *Sci Rep* 2018; **8**: 16769. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-34979-3>

⁴ Charlwood JD, Rowland M, Protopopoff N, Le Clair C. The Furvela tent-trap Mk 1.1 for the collection of outdoor biting mosquitoes. *PeerJ* 2017; **5**:e3848 <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.3848>

Figure Legend

Figure 1 Knockdown times of susceptible *Anopheles arabiensis* from Muleba, Tanzania, exposed to a new Olyset net (n= 4 replicates of 25 mosquitoes per replicate) and resistant *An. funestus* from Furvela, Mozambique exposed to used Interceptor, which killed susceptible *An. arabiensis*, (n= 13 replicates of 25 mosquitoes per replicate) or a new Permanet (n= 1 replicate of 27 mosquitoes per replicate). Resistance status based on standard WHO assays.

